

INTERBREEDING AND FRUITING IN FOREIGN GRAPE VARIETIES

Xakimov Shaxbozbek Shavkatbek ugli

Master of Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

Abstract: Intraspecific recurrent selection in *V. vinifera* is an effective method for breeding of high quality, disease-, cold-, and drought-resistance grapes. Exploring the optimal treatment methods for grape (*V. vinifera*) seeds can help to accelerate the process of intraspecific recurrent selection and improve breeding efficiency. In this study, seeds of six *V. vinifera* varieties were used as experimental materials, and the germination and seedling formation characteristics were studied by single factor treatment and orthogonal compound treatment, respectively. To do this, stratification, chemical substances, beak cutting, and pre-germination treatments were tested, and the optimal treatment combination was determined for each variety. The results indicated that the optimal conditions obtained in the orthogonal experiments were not completely consistent with those in the single-factor experiments. Single factor experiment results demonstrated that two stratification methods (chilling gauze-storage and chilling sand-storage) and two pre-germination methods (pre-germination in petri dishes and pre-germination in a bean sprouter) vary in effectiveness for different varieties. gibberellin acid (GA3) soaking and beak-cutting promote the germination and seedling rate of the tested varieties. Orthogonal test results demonstrate that, for Dunkelfelder and Cabernet Sauvignon, the optimal treatment combination was chilling sand-storage + GA3 soaking seed + beak cutting + pre-germination in petri dishes. For Meili, the optimal treatment combination was chilling sand-storage + acetic acid (HAc) soaking seed + beak cutting + pre-germination in petri dishes. For Ecolly, the optimal treatment combination was chilling sand-storage + GA3 soaking seed + beak cutting + pre-germination in a bean sprouter. For Garanior, the optimal treatment combination was chilling sand-storage + HAc soaking seed + no beak cutting + pre-germination in petri dishes. For Marselan, the optimal treatment combination was chilling gauze-

storage + GA3 soaking seed + beak cutting + pre-germination in a bean sprouter. This study identified the optimal conditions for seed germination and seedling formation of six grape varieties, which will facilitate future work to characterize the seed germination and seedling formation of seeds obtained by intraspecific hybridization of these varieties. This work also provides a reference for addressing problems of low seed germination rate and suboptimal seedling formation for better utilization of grape germplasms.

Keywords: *V. vinifera*; grape seeds; seed germination; seedling formation

Grapes have been cultivated and bred for more than 200 years. The successful breeding of different grape varieties for different purposes requires high-quality grape genetic resources and typically a variety of breeding methods and techniques have been used. Breeding is done to improve the quality of grapes, including enhanced resistance of plants to biological and abiotic stress or an extended or shortened maturity period to meet market needs [1]. Hybrid breeding and seed selection are important aspects of the breeding process [2]. As the most widely cultivated grape with the highest economic value in the world, *V. vinifera* is widely used as the main material for breeding new grape varieties [3,4]. Intraspecific recurrent selection in *V. vinifera* is an effective method for breeding of high quality, disease-, cold-, and drought-resistance grapes [4]. However, more effective breeding strategies require improved germination and seedling formation rates of intraspecific hybrid seeds in *V. vinifera*, to obtain larger seedling populations in a short time and enable more rapid grape breeding. The cultivation of seeds into seedlings is one of the most important determinants of breeding efficiency. The germination rate of grape seeds is typically low, 30–50%, with a final seedling rate that is even lower [5–6]. Low germination rates can be due to the selection of parents, an incompletely developed seed embryo of the female parent, or a hard seed coat that is not easy to crack [5]. During seed collection and storage, seeds that are not fully mature or subjected to improper temperature and humidity during storage can result in seed decay or premature germination [4]. If the stratification time is too long or too short,

the phenolic compounds in seeds can inhibit the germination rate [2]. Humidity can be difficult to control when trying to germinate seeds. If the humidity is too low, the germination rate will be low due to a lack of water, but if the humidity is too high, seeds are prone to mold and rot [5]. After sowing, the seedling stage may suffer blight or be inhibited by improper cultivation conditions [3]. Previous studies on grape seed germination and seedling formation examined differences of germination rates among different populations and varieties, differences of seedling formation rates among different cultivation and transplanting methods or characterized the physiology of germination and the optimal way to release dormancy [1]. Chai et al. compared the germination and seedling rates of cultivars *V. vinifera*, *V. labrusca*, and Franco-American, with *V. vinifera* and Franco-American varieties displaying higher and lower germination rates, respectively [2,5]. Grape seeds experience physiological dormancy, and the dormancy degree and method of dormancy release differ among different varieties [4]. Pan et al. studied the effects of gibberellin acid (GA3) on the seed germination characteristics of *V. adenoclada* Hand. -Mazz, *V. davidi*, wine grape, and table grape, finding that GA3 significantly improved the germination rate, germination potential, and germination index of grape seeds, and shortened the length of germination [5]. In addition, effects of 6-benzyl aminopurine (6-BA), Forchior fennron (CPUU), acetic acid (HAc), polyethylene glycol, indole acetic acid, 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, lime nitrogen, ammonium nitrate, and other chemicals on seed germination rate were described [2]. Zhang et al. investigated the effects of direct sowing seeds in field or in a greenhouse and evaluated the use of film mulching of seedlings in the field and in a greenhouse. The highest formation rate of hybrid seedlings was obtained by sowing seeds in a greenhouse with the hole disc method and then transplanting the seedlings to the field in mid to late May after the growth of 4–5 true leaves [3]. An understanding of dormancy, germination, and seedling formation in grape seeds remains lacking, and more comprehensive studies are needed. In this study, six grape varieties were used as intraspecific hybrid parents. Single factor and orthogonal test systems were used to analyze the influences of different stratification methods of chilling gauze-storage

and chilling sand-storage on germination and seedling rates, the effects of chemical treatments on seed dormancy before germination, the influence of cutting beak on germination and seedling rates, and the efficacy of pre-germination methods using petri dishes or a bean sprouter to improve germination and seedling rates. The aim of this study was to provide technical reference to improve the germination and seedling formation of the intraspecific hybrid progenies of six grape varieties of *V. vinifera* and increase the efficiency of recurrent selection.

Temperature and humidity are key factors for seed germination and also important environmental conditions for seed germination effect [1]. Different treatments may be more effective for different varieties based on differences in morphological structure and growth characteristics [5]. The results demonstrated significant effects on the germinating rate and potential of Dunkelfelder by chilling sand-storage. The seed coat of Dunkelfelder is hard, and humidity is low during stratification. This could limit seed expansion, resulting in slow germination and low germination rate [6]. Chemical treatments can change the internal metabolic mechanism of seeds, relieve seed dormancy, and promote seed germination [2]. The results of this study demonstrated that GA3, 6-BA, CPUU, and HAc improved the germination rate, potential, and index of grape seeds of the tested varieties, with GA3 providing the largest treatment effect. This is consistent with the results of previous studies [4]. This may be because GA3, as a plant growth regulator, participates in the signal transmission during seed germination, and improves the activity of various enzymes to accelerate the decomposition and synthesis of internal substances in seeds, to improve the germination rate, potential, and index of the seeds [3]. Beakcutting treatments also improved the germination rate, potential, and index of the tested varieties, which was consistent with the results of previous studies [2]. During seed germination, the control of humidity is particularly important. When the humidity is too low, the seed germination rate will be affected because of water limitation, but high humidity can make seeds become moldy and rotten [5]. Pre-germination in a bean sprouter also improved germination, with different effects

observed for different varieties. This effect may be related to the constant humidity during pre-germination in a bean sprouter [3].

Seed germination is the first stage of life in which plants can perceive the external environment, and this is also the most sensitive stage to environmental changes [4]. Germination directly affects seedling emergence and subsequent growth [5]. There were very significant differences in the influence of the two stratification methods on the emergence and seedling rates of Dunkelfelder. This may be due to the better relative swelling effect of seeds in the sand storage process, which improved germination and seedling formation [6]. Varieties with high germination efficiency and rate can more easily produce seedlings under appropriate environmental conditions [6]. There was no difference in the effects of different chemical treatments on the emergence and seedling rates of Meili, Dunkelfelder, and Cabernet Sauvignon, but there were different effects on the emergence and seedling rates of Ecolly, Garanior, and Marselan, potentially related to the relatively higher germination rate and potential of these varieties. Seed germination and seedling growth are the beginning stage of the plant life cycle, and exogenous treatment affects seed vigor [3]. Beak-cutting treatments improved the germination rate, potential, and index of the six tested varieties, but also improved the emergence and seedling rates, consistent with the results of previous studies [2]. Increasing the seedling rate can conserve resources [4]. The emergence and seedling rates of Ecolly and Cabernet Sauvignon were increased by pregermination in a bean sprouter, but these rates were decreased for Garanior, Dunkelfelder, and Marselan. This may be related to differences between varieties, such as seed maturity, endogenous hormone content, seed coat thickness, thousand-grain weight, size, water content, dormancy type, and the amount of cold needed to break dormancy [5]. In addition, we found that for all exogenous treatments, the seedling and emergence rates of the six tested varieties had a similar ratio, which may be related to the use of a seed coating agent before germination. Previous studies have found that a seed coating agent exhibits a good prevention and control effect on seedling stage wilt disease, which greatly increases the seedling rate [6].

References

1. Fang, J.; Liu, C. Grape Genetics, Breeding and Genomics; Jiangsu Science & Technology Press: Nanjing, China, 2014.
2. Chai, J. Comparison of germination rate and seedling percentage of different grape cultivars. *Hebei J. For. Orchard. Res.* 2005, 20, 64–66+75. [CrossRef]
3. Huang, X.; Shao, Y.; Gao, A.; Feng, J.; Xu, L. The Analysis of Domestic Documents About *Vitis vinifera* L. in China. *J. Libr. Inf. Sci. Agric.* 2005, 17, 136–139. [CrossRef]
4. Wang, Z.L.; Xue, T.T.; Gao, F.F.; Zhang, L.; Han, X.; Wang, Y.; Hui, M.; Wu, D.; Li, H.; Wang, H. Intraspecific recurrent selection in *V. vinifera*: An effective method for breeding of high quality, disease-, cold-, and drought-resistant grapes. *Euphytica* 2021, 217, 111. [CrossRef]
5. Lin, L.; Zhang, Y.; Huang, Y.; Peng, H.; Hu, J. A comparative study on seed germination in different grape cultivars. *Guangxi Agric. Sci.* 2009, 40, 1590–1592. [CrossRef]
6. Liu, H.; Wang, Y. Effect of medicament treatments on grape seed germination. *Deciduous Fruits* 2001, 33, 10–11. [CrossRef]